

XR Etudes for Augmented Piano

Giovanni Santini

Xi'an Jiaotong - Liverpool University
giovanni.santini@xjtlu.edu.cn

ABSTRACT

Studi sulla Realtà Nuova (in English, *Etudes on the New Real*) is a cycle of etudes created to explore the possibilities of XR in the context of live multimedia performance. Although many etudes have been created, only three etudes have been performed in public. Two of them are for augmented piano. The performer wears an Augmented Reality (AR) headset and hand trackers. This setup allows them to interact with Virtual Objects (VOs) and control visuals and audio. The environment used for the XR performance allows one to control up to 7 different video output and an n-speaker 3D audio configuration. VOs, as well as audio-visual outputs, react to the performer's gesture. The different aspects of performance develop following a pseudo-narrative outline. One of the key points of interest is the relationship between performer and audience, specifically in terms of transfer of the immersive experience: while the performer is immersed in an AR space, the audience can only see 2D screens. The experimented solution consisted in providing multiple projections and spatial audio. The paper will describe the etudes realized for augmented piano, from a technical and artistic point of view. Space will be also given to the discussion of issues in instrumental performance in an XR setting.

1. INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality or Realities (XR) can be considered an umbrella term that includes Virtual Reality (purely virtual worlds), Augmented Reality (merging of Virtual Objects, VOs, with the real environment) and some other technical solutions that deal with the concept of immersive experience. An example are CAVEs, rooms fully covered with projections, used to re-create a sort of virtual landscape.

Following from this definition, an application of XR to live performance could present the simultaneous adoption of different technological solutions (e.g., AR + projections), thus creating a hybrid experience.

Specifically, the work described in this paper starts from augmented instruments in an Augmented Reality context (from the point of view of the performer) and then expands it into multiple projections (coupled with spatial audio) for the audience. *Studi sulla Realtà Nuova* (*Etudes on the New*

Real) is a set of etudes for XR multimedia performance. Most of the etudes have been created for piano and two of them have been performed in public. This paper will focus on the description of these two etudes from a technical and artistic point of view. They will be referred to as *Studi* from now on.

These etudes are created with the intention to explore the technical and expressive possibilities of augmented piano in an XR context, each of them insisting on one specific technical constraint. In such a context, the concept of "technical constraint" can be faced on several layers: performing technique, interaction design, compositional technique, visuals, and audio. The concept behind *Studi* is to connect a reduced amount of material on all the levels and tie them to a pseudo-narrative structure.

This paper will detail how this connection is conceived, while also describing the technical implementation and the issues related to instrumental performance in an XR context.

2. BACKGROUND

The use of sensors to enhance the possibilities of musical live performance is rooted in the concepts of hyperinstruments and augmented instruments. In the first case, performance gestures are tracked and converted into data in order to control algorithmic parameters. Those parameters are, in some way, related to the production of sound (synthesized and/or processed). The main idea is to create a virtual interface, or virtual instrument, such that performance gestures are directly related to the production of sound. The advantage of creating a virtual instrument is that the mapping gesture-sound can be redefined at any moment [1]. Similar principles can be applied in general to the idea of Digital Musical Instruments, although in that case the control interface might not be virtual but physical. However, the arbitrary selection of mappings between performer's action and sound result is still one of the main focuses. Actually, the way the interaction is designed, qualifies the instrument [2]. In the case of augmented instruments, sensors are used to enhance the possibility of a physical instrument. Sensors can be used to track performance gestures or interaction with physical interfaces added to the body of the instrument [3]. The sound processing/synthesis is then in "dialogue" with the acoustic sound. The advent of Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR) enriched this landscape with the possibility to add visual elements that behave consistently with the spatial gestures of the performer. Thus, the new category of Virtual Reality Musical Instruments (VRMIs) [4]. Similarly, some augmented instru-

ments have been crafted using augmented reality technology, e.g. Amy Brandon's *Augmented Percussions* (2019) and [5].

Notation has also been expanded into the VR/AR field and sometimes integrated into the concept of virtual instrument, with immersive interactive scores [6], interactive VR/AR notation [7], and live-generated spatial notation [8].

The question of the transfer of the immersive VR/AR experience from the performer to the audience is still an open question: equipping every person with a headset poses technical and financial challenges, thus leaving 2D projection as the most used option to approximate that experience [9]. In this sense, efforts have been made to push the boundaries. In some cases, projections are aligned to the spatial position and gestures of the performer in such a way that the interaction results spatially coherent, thus increasing the perception of immersivity [10–12].

In [13] multiple projections with moving screens are employed in order to re-create the idea of VR performance. Many other experiences used similar solutions [14].

In *Studi*, the author wanted to deal, on one side, with the idea of instrumental augmentation in AR, on the other side with the question of immersive experience for the audience. The result is an XR performance that makes use of multiple projections and spatial audio.

3. ENVIRONMENT

A necessary element for the creation of *Studi* was the development of an environment handling the multiple technological components of the XR pieces: tracking, interaction, an AR scene for the performer, multiple video outputs for the audience and spatial audio. To achieve that, several applications running in parallel needed to be developed.

Figure 1. Scheme of the system. The grey objects were implemented in the design but not used during the performance for contingent reasons.

Originally, the environment was designed to provide 7 video outputs and spatial audio. That required four different machines. The main computer (PC1), controlling the other machines via OSC, was connected to the AR headset worn by the pianist. It ran the AR application that handles tracking, interaction with VOs and generates the AR visuals for the performer (mirrored to a projector). It also

generated control data for the other machines. Other two computers ran applications that generated video output:

- PC2 was connected to an additional AR stereo camera providing an AR point of view from a different angle. It also produced video output of a virtual camera (originally, should have been 2).
- PC3 generated one video output from a virtual camera. Originally, it was meant to render one more virtual camera and the feed of a normal mono camera with superimposed AR (the main difference with the AR camera attached to PC 2 was the lack of spatial analysis and therefore the lack of advanced AR features such as spatial occlusion¹).

PC2 and PC3 ran a modified version of the application on PC1. The applications were developed in Unity. During the performance, for contingent issues (displacement of projectors too far away from the machines) the number of total video outputs had to be cut down to 4. 3 machines still needed to be used for video output. See Figure 1.

PC4 was dedicated to audio processing and spatial audio (tested in 24.2 ch 3D audio system, then in concert venue on an 8-ch 2D system). PC4 was running a Max/MSP patch.

3.1 AR app for the performer and additional video outputs

The performer wears an AR headset (HTC Vive Pro 2 with a Zed Mini) and Vive trackers attached to the hands. This way, they can interact with VOs and control audio and visual outputs. In the AR scene, interactive VOs are shown, conveniently placed around the keyboard. The interaction happens either through virtual contact or through gazing (the app tracks when the performer is looking at some object). VOs typically react in their own way (different VOs react in different ways).

Upon interaction, depending on the VO, either event numbers or position/rotation vectors are used to generate interactive visuals both in the AR application on PC1 and on the other computers. Those machines run a modified version of the AR app, designed in a way to receive control data from the main computer instead of gathering those data from the direct tracking of the performer. The modified apps also contain additional assets and cameras for the additional projections.

Data is also sent to the audio program, in order to trigger cues (updating multiple parameters' values at once) and/or control specific processing parameters.

3.2 Audio

The audio program in Figure 2 has three basic tasks:

- Playing back different audio files, controlled by the VOs interaction on PC1

¹ When a real object is between a VO and the camera, the VO should not be rendered or result partly covered by the real object. Occlusion is crucial in providing the perception of convincing and accurate spatial displacement

Figure 2. Screenshot of the Max/MSP patch. The objects visualised in presentation mode are just for fast debugging. During the concert, the electronics was completely controlled by the AR software on PC1 via OSC. No extra performer was required.

- Controlling a granulator. The tool is regulated through numerous parameters, such as: grain size, loudness, transposition, density, probability of activation, voice-related glissando, grain-related glissando, “single event vs continuous sound” trigger, resonance filter frequency, resonance and gain and their behaviour over time, etc. The high number of parameters requires a scheduling system able to change all the parameters at once upon specific interactions; otherwise, few parameters (grain size, density, transposition, resonant filter resonance and frequency) can be controlled by the hands position and rotation.
- Controlling the sound spatialization. The spatialization was tested with a 3D VBAP panning on a 24.2 system, but during the performance, due to the strong reverb of the venue, an angular panning was chosen over a 2D 8ch system (sacrificing smooth spatial transitions to clarity of localization). Every single voice of the granulator is spatialized independently.

4. ARTISTIC CONCEPTION

From an artistic standpoint, three main issues are worth noticing:

- musical notation
- issues related to the performance
- creative process for an XR piece

4.1 Musical notation

The two etudes, *Ghiaccio* and *Zyleb*, are notated in Common Western Music Notation. The score also indicates the types of VOs the performer is required to interact with and the timing.

Figure 3. Part of the score of *Ghiaccio*.

For example, in Figure 3, different interfaces are indicated with different colors. Black noteheads mean to play on the keys. The notes in green refer to a fretted instrument whose pitch mapping can be changed when touching a virtual sphere (the same fret will return a different pitch), hence the writing “Trigger Configuration 4”. The light-blue notehead indicates a harmony trigger modeled as an interactable water layer. The yellow notehead indicates a spinning planet activated when the performer looks at it. It also changes harmonies but with a different timbre. Figure 4 presents a frame capture of the performance of the passage above.

Since the behaviour of VOS depends on events and follows a scheduling system, according to a pseudo-narrative development, the score can also be considered a script.

Figure 4. Frontal view of the performance setup. One projection on a wall is not in the camera view.

4.2 Issues related to the performance

The spatial disposition of VOs needs to take into account the physicality of the performance. The interpreter is required to play the keys while also interacting with VOs. Consequently, VOs need to be positioned in such a way

that both actions are feasible and comfortable. The size also matters. In fact, the collision detection is prone to small, but noticeable, spatial errors. Additionally, collisions could not be detected if they happen too fast (if the collision lasts less than the duration of a frame² and happens between frames). For this reason, interfaces need to be large enough to allow robustness of detection. As a rule of thumb, the size along one of the XYZ axes should not be less than 15 cm. The gesture then needs to be rehearsed, in order to obtain spatial precision. A fast gesture, running along the longest side of the VO, is also recommended, especially when the score requires perfect synchronization.

It is also worth discussing the impact of the AR device itself on the performance. A VR headset with a pass-through stereo camera was preferred to a see-through AR device (such as Hololens 2). The downside of this choice is a slight limitation of the real-world field of view and a slightly different perception of depth. These two aspects have some impact on how the keyboard is perceived and require the performer to adapt to the different feeling. The problem with see-through AR headsets is that the field of view for seeing the VOs is dramatically reduced. They are visible only inside a small square in front of the eyes³. This limitation would have strongly constrained the level of complexity of the physical actions required. In fact, the peripheral view is necessary when the performer is assigned a complex set of actions. In other terms, the pianist cannot always be looking straight in the direction of VOs.

The use of Vive trackers also needs some discussion. With those attached on their hands, the physical perception of the keyboard sharply differs from the usual. The pianist needs to re-adjust to the different feeling and learn a specific set of movements. However, a very reliable hands tracking is required, as gestures need to be fast and hands tend to move constantly and within a broad range. Other solutions, such as camera-based tracking⁴, would have presented potential failure points: the hands movements would certainly fall out of the view of the camera repeatedly. Also, the stability and robustness of single-camera tracking is not optimal, in the author's experience.

4.3 Creative process for an XR piece

At the conceptual core of *Studi*, there is the idea of connecting acoustic sound, electronic sound, visuals (with multiple video outputs), interaction and pseudo-narrative development. The choice was made to create such connections using simple, quite self-explanatory ideas.

One preliminary point to make is that electronic sound is at the same time a necessary component of the audio texture and a part of the reaction of a VO to the collision with the performer's hands. The creation of the electronic processing needs to take into account this double nature: the behaviour of sound somehow needs to be coherent with

² The frame duration is the time elapsed between the rendering of two consecutive images (frames) that constitute the video output.

³ 43 degrees on the vertical axis, 29 on the horizontal axis for Hololens2.

⁴ Professional motion capture camera arrays are not considered in this case, as those are very impractical to move across different venues, and the gain for the performance would not justify the logistic complexity.

the visual behaviour of the interface.

Ghiaccio (Ice) is meditative, cold, distant. Visual references are water, rain, snow, ice and the cold outer space inhabited by planets. The instrumental writing makes use of slow arpeggios that extend across the keyboard. The electronic sound is made of slowly changing harmonies, with the use of different timbres. Harmonies change upon the interaction with VOs, modeled as layers of water and spinning planets. All the reactions are gradual and follow a fade-in, fade-out approach, with a behaviour that mirrors the behaviour of the electronic sound. In the fourth section, a fretted ice cube materializes above the keyboard. The performer plays it with the right hand, while playing the keyboard with the left hand. At the same time, virtual rain and snow fall inside the venue.

Zyleb is built around the idea of impulse, violence and obsession. The instrumental writing mostly makes use of a fast *ostinato*, obsessive, with emerging accents. The electronic processing makes use of a granulator, which can both generate continuous textures or single percussive events. Virtual interfaces are pointy particle effects which explode in shards when touched. Later, they evolve in fountains (which control continuous sounds) and a virtual drum placed on the side of the piano (for impulsive sounds). The interaction design relies on events, moments of collision between hands and virtual objects. The musical structure is designed to have these collisions perfectly aligned with the rhythmic grid. In the context of XR performance, and especially considering the current stage of technology available on the consumer market, the technical challenge of this requirement is actually quite remarkable.

The approximation of an immersive experience for the audience was also a central theme of the artistic conception. Some of the multiple video outputs were designed to feature additional AR cameras from a different point of view. However, some other projections were conceived as a "virtual comment" to the performance. They would feature virtual cameras (i.e. without the real-world image) which would sometimes move around at the same virtual objects used for the AR scene but with a virtual background. This would add a fresh perspective to visuals. In other circumstances, they could show layers of water, snow, or rain. They could also show a different virtual scene. The concept of immersivity was not taken "literally" (recreate one space in 360 degrees) but rather metaphorically (create different points of view and visual inputs so that to reconstruct an embracing context).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has described two XR pieces from the cycle *Studi sulla Realtà Nuova*, for augmented piano in XR. In those pieces, the author wanted to deal with specific technical and aesthetic issues, focusing on a narrow selection of ideas for each of them. The inter-connection of the different layers (acoustic sound, electronics, visuals and interaction design) was a core principle informing the whole creative process. AR scene for the performer, audio and visuals were generated by different networked computers, controlled by a main via OSC protocol. The problem of

the transfer of the immersive experience to the audience was faced by employing multiple projections and spatial audio.

Visual documentation of the concert can be found at <https://www.giovannisantini.com/studi>

Acknowledgments

This research was realized with the support of the Hong Kong University Grant Committee, Fazioli, the Hong Kong Italian Institute of Culture, Osage Foundation and Tom Lee Music.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Machover, "Hyperinstruments - a progress report 1987-1991," MIT Media Laboratories, Tech. Rep., 1992.
- [2] J. Malloch, D. Birnbaum, E. Sinyor, and M. M. Wanderley, "Towards a new conceptual framework for digital musical instruments," in *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Digital Audio Effects*, 2006.
- [3] B. Frédéric, N. Rasamimanana, E. Fléty, S. Lemouton, and F. Baschet, "The Augmented Violin Project: reseach, composition and performance report," *Proceedings of the 2006 International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME), Paris, France*, 2006.
- [4] S. Serafin, C. Erkut, J. Kojs, N. C. Nilsson, and R. Nordahl, "Virtual Reality Musical Instruments: State of the Art, Design Principles, and Future Directions," *Computer Music Journal*, 2016.
- [5] G. Santini, "Augmented Piano in Augmented Reality," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, 2020.
- [6] D. Kim-Boyle, "3D notations and the immersive score," *Leonardo Music Journal*, 2019.
- [7] A. Brandon, "Hidden Motive: on the development of interactive graphic scores for AR and VR," *The Association of Canadian Women Composers (ACWC)*, pp. 19–28, 2018.
- [8] G. Santini, "Composition as an embodied act: A framework for the gesture-based creation of augmented reality action scores," in *Proceedings of the Sound and Music Computing Conferences*, 2020.
- [9] L. Turchet, R. Hamilton, and A. Camci, "Music in Extended Realities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, 2021.
- [10] S. F. Alaoui, C. Jacquemin, and F. Bevilacqua, "Chiseling Bodies: an Augmented Dance Performance," in *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings*, vol. 2013-April, 2013.
- [11] A. Clay, G. Domenger, J. Conan, A. Domenger, and N. Couture, "Integrating augmented reality to enhance expression, interaction and collaboration in live performances: A ballet dance case study," in *ISMAR 2014 - IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality - Media, Arts, Social Science, Humanities and Design 2014, Proceedings*, 2014.
- [12] A. Bluff and A. Johnston, "Devising interactive theatre: Trajectories of production with complex Bespoke technologies," in *DIS 2019 - Proceedings of the 2019 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference*, 2019.
- [13] D. Gochfeld, A. Coulombe, Y.-J. Yeh, R. Lester, R. B. Fleming, Z. Meicher-Buzzi, and A. Tarr, "A Tale of Two Productions: A Christmas Carol On Stage and in Virtual Reality," in *Proceedings of the ACM on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques*, 2022.
- [14] J. Weijdom, "Mixed Reality and the Theatre of the Future. Fresh Perspectives on Arts and New Technologies." Vol 6. *IETM - International Network for Contemporary Performing Arts*, 2017.